

ResC4EU
RESILIENT SUPPLY CHAINS FOR EUROPE

Interactive Demonstrator

... **Industrial Symbiosis for Resource
and Material Savings**

Try it now

<https://resc4eu.greentwin.app/demonstrator-2>

Overview

This demonstrator presents Industrial Symbiosis enabling the synergistic exchanges of waste streams, by-products, waste, and energy among companies within a local, industrial, or retail ecosystem. Industrial Symbiosis is a collaborative approach linked to the circular economy and focused on identifying underutilized resources in one company and matching them with the needs of another. This involves learning from other sectors and facilitating their reintegration into the value chain. This practice promotes enhanced resource efficiency and waste reduction, advancing the principles of the circular economy into practice. This demonstrator is an interactive simulation that allows users to compare conventional supply chains with Industrial Symbiosis alternatives. It is publicly accessible via the ResC4EU platform: <https://resc4eu.greentwin.app/demonstrator-2>

Resource Comparison Data

The main synergies associated with each resource are as follows:

Resource	Unit	Industrial symbiosis energy consumption	Standard energy consumption
Water	1 m ³	0.4 kWh/m ³	0.3 kWh/m ³
Energy	1 kWh	0 kg CO ₂ eq/kWh*	European mix
Raw materials	1 kg	0.02 kWh/kg	3.0 kWh/kg

* this value is a Global Warming Potential (GWP)

Company Data

The table below shows the companies included in the demonstrator and the resources offered by each. Users will be able to select from these companies during the demonstration.

Company	Resources
A	Raw materials, water
B	Raw materials
C	Energy, water
D	Raw materials, water
E	Raw materials, energy

About the ResC4EU Project

The ResC4EU project aims to support EU businesses, especially small and medium sized enterprises (SMEs), to become more resilient and sustainable and be able to quickly adapt to supply chain disruptions such as experienced during COVID-19 crisis, geopolitical tensions or disasters by adopting advanced technologies. ResC4EU will provide an open space for collaboration, develop and provide models and tools that can assist SMEs in detecting and anticipating disruptions in their supply chains, and offering SMEs tailored support and training programmes as part of the ResC4EU Net-Zero Industry Academies. Further, manufacturing SMEs in need of implementing advanced technologies will be brought together with tech-savvy SMEs providing innovative solutions.

For more details: <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101137643/results>

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AIDIMME
INSTITUTO TECNOLÓGICO

Demonstrator Owner

AIDIMME, [HTTPS://WWW.AIDIMME.ES/](https://www.aidimme.es/)

María José Núñez Ariño, mjnunez@aidimme.es

Ángel Marcos Vicente, amarcos@aidimme.es